

RESEARCH ON LIPSTICK USAGE TRENDS AMONG VIETNAMESE GEN Z YOUTH

NGUYEN THI VAN ANH ¹, PHAM THANH THUY ² and NGUYEN CHIEU KHANH ³

¹ PhD, University of Labor and Social Affairs.

² Associate, PhD, Banking Academy of Vietnam.

³ Annie Wright Schools Tacoma, WA.

Abstract

Research article on lipstick usage trends of Vietnamese youth. Using qualitative research methods combined with a survey of 276 young people in provinces and cities of Vietnam, the study has shown the main trends in the selection and use of lipstick by young people today. You choose and use lipstick based on many criteria such as suitability to your own preferences, depending on the occasions of using lipstick. Besides, the trend of using lipstick of young people is also influenced by celebrities, people around them and young people often use lipstick according to trends, use lipstick for many purposes and have a variety of designs, styles, colors and origins of each type of lipstick. At the same time, the study also points out the concerns of young people in choosing and using lipstick lines, discovering the future trends in lipstick use that they are aiming for, such as choosing lipstick lines of natural origin, safe, benign and environmentally friendly. From the analysis of lipstick usage trends of young people, the research team proposed some exchanges and discussions to promote the lipstick market in Vietnam to be able to meet the trends and needs of young Vietnamese people.

Keywords: Lipstick, Lipstick Usage Trends, Gen Z, Vietnamese Youth.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Vietnamese cosmetics market is on the rise, especially in the export sector. Cosmetics are gradually becoming an indispensable necessity in life. Grasping that, many cosmetic brands are gradually appearing and occupying a large market, besides the 4.0 era has created many opportunities as well as presented competition in the industry.

Currently, 90% of Vietnamese cosmetic enterprises are distribution agents of foreign partners. (Danh, Nguyen Tran, 2022) In addition to famous international cosmetic brands, the Vietnamese market also witnessed the strong development of domestic cosmetic brands. Cosmetic companies have gradually grasped the trends and needs of domestic consumers. The cosmetics market in general in Vietnam also shows development in distribution channels. In addition to traditional stores, supermarkets and cosmetic chains, consumers can also buy products through online channels and e-commerce platforms. (VKI, n.d).

Lipstick has cast a spell over cultures throughout history. From the past to the present, the little tube of colour, oil and wax has been scorned, shunned and embraced (Madeleine Ogilvie and Pauline Kristensen-Bach, 2001). Lipstick has become an indispensable item for women in general from the past until today.

Lipstick represents beauty, confidence and individuality in a woman's style and preferences. Lipstick helps women shine and be confident, because lipstick is not only a simple makeup product but also an object associated with women.

Nowadays, lipstick is still an indispensable item for women, especially young people. As society develops, the demand for lipstick lines becomes more diverse. In particular, young people are a generation of smart consumers, with many distinct characteristics compared to the previous generation, so the trend of using lipstick has also become more different.

Today's youth, in addition to choosing lipsticks with elegant colors, suitable for skin tone and personality, exuding confidence and luxury, also tend to use lipsticks of natural origin, safe and benign to human health, and friendly to the environment.

Research the lipstick usage trends of young people to find out what their tastes are for lipstick colors and what conditions lipstick quality needs to meet. And researching lipstick usage trends to develop the lipstick market in Vietnam, meeting the needs of young people, besides, supporting lipstick manufacturing and trading enterprises in Vietnam to be able to come up with appropriate strategies, both meeting market standards and ensuring environmental factors, increasing revenue and profits, developing the lipstick and cosmetics market in general.

2. OVERVIEW OF LIPSTICK PRODUCTS AND CONSUMER HABITS OF VIETNAMESE GEN Z

2.1. Concepts

There are many sources of information and definitions about lipstick products. Simply put, lipstick is a cosmetic used to beautify the lips, helping to conceal imperfections on the lips while also having the ability to nourish and protect your lips to make them more beautiful and smoother. (Bio Cosmetics, n.d).

According to M.O.I Cosmetics (n.d), Lipstick is a cosmetic that when applied to the lips will create a beautiful color, can cover up defects on the lips or protect your lips. Lipsticks are made with a variety of ingredients such as oils, waxes, colorants, emollients, and skin conditioners...

2.2. Ingredients of Lipstick

According to Vinmec (n.d), Lipstick ingredients are mainly made up of wax, oil and colorants:

Colorants: helps create color for lipstick and is divided into 2 types: inorganic colorants and organic colorants. Inorganic colors commonly used are iron oxide, TiO₂, ZnO, pearl powder which are insoluble, so appropriate preparation techniques are required to evenly disperse the color. Organic colors such as beetroot red, Anthocyanins, Lactoflavin are soluble, easy to disperse evenly but cause color smudging. Therefore, they are often combined together to create lipsticks that do not smudge and are even in color.

Wax: Wax is the ingredient that creates the shape of the lipstick, while also creating shine, smoothness and adhesion of the lipstick. Some natural waxes commonly used to make lipstick include beeswax, Carnuba wax, Candelila wax and lanolin wax, hydrocarbons such as paraffin, ozokerite.

Oil: Oil has the effect of moisturizing, making lips soft and smooth and dissolving colorants or other soluble substances in lipstick. The most commonly used oil in lipstick manufacturing is castor oil.

In addition, there are grape seed oil, almond oil, palm oil, olive oil, cocoa butter, jojoba, linolin, IPM, IPP, mineral oil, triglyceride, dimethicone, cyclomethicone, vegetable oil. *Besides the 3 main ingredients, some lipsticks also contain the following ingredients:*

Preservatives and antioxidants: These help maintain the shelf life of the lipstick as the ingredients will oxidize over time. On average, a lipstick can only be used for 1 year, when preservatives and antioxidants are added, it can be used longer.

Fragrances: Artificial fragrances are often used to mask the scent of chemical ingredients in oils, waxes and colorants found in lipsticks. For people who often have dry, chapped lips, they should limit the use of scented lipsticks because they can cause skin irritation.

2.3. Types of Lipstick

According to Bio Cosmetics (n.d) and M.O.I Cosmetics (n.d), there are many lipstick lines on the market with a variety of designs, colors and qualities. Highlights are the 7 most popular lipsticks on the market today:

Matte Lipstick

The most popular lipstick line today because of its ability to give standard and long-lasting color with a lasting color of 5 to 6 hours and then gradually fading. In terms of advantages, matte lipstick is very durable, has no glossy effect, has standard color, covers lip defects and has long-lasting color. However, the disadvantage of this lipstick line is that it dries the lips, so users need to moisturize their lips carefully before applying lipstick.

Lipstick

Cream lipstick is also a type of lipstick that many people love. The lipstick has a liquid texture and high moisture content to keep lips soft and smooth, keeping color on the lips longer. Lipstick is usually stored in a glass bottle and applied with a brush. The advantage of this lipstick line is that it has more wax than oil, is extremely waterproof, and does not lose color after eating or drinking due to its high color fastness. However, the disadvantage of this lipstick is that it makes the lips dry and heavy due to the wax content.

Lip Gloss

Lip gloss is a type of lipstick that when applied to the lips creates a glossy effect. Gel lipstick is usually designed in two forms: one is a tube, the other is a glass bottle with a large brush. This lipstick line has the advantage of creating a glossy, attractive and impressive lip color, with fresh colors and a variety of lipsticks for users to choose from.

However, the limitation of this lipstick line is that the color is slow, fades quickly, sometimes feels sticky if you are not used to it and can easily get on other places if you are not careful when applying lipstick.

Tint Lipstick

This is a lipstick line with a light liquid texture like water, usually contained in a glass bottle and used with a brush to apply. With the best color adhesion among lipsticks and a light liquid texture, when applying lipstick, the user does not feel heavy. However, the ability of lip tint to conceal lip defects is poor, so it should not be used for dark lips. On the other hand, due to its high color adhesion, it is difficult to remove makeup when using this lipstick line.

Satin Lipstick

This is a lipstick line also known as moisturizing matte lipstick. Lipstick line with hybrid characteristics between lip balm and matte lipstick. With many advantages such as: the lipstick contains more lip care ingredients than other lipsticks, suitable for many different lip types, the lipstick has a light shine and is not too matte but still covers lip defects and does not dry lips, the color is relatively standard. However, this lipstick line still has some limitations such as color durability is not highly rated, only keeping color for 4-5 hours.

Lip Balm

Lip balm is a lipstick line that contains many nutrients to replenish lips with vitality. Lipstick often contains many ingredients such as aloe vera, vitamin E, coconut oil, aloe vera... Lipsticks come in both colored and colorless varieties, so you can choose whichever one suits your needs. The advantage of this lipstick line is its ability to provide the lips with necessary nutrients, helping to keep the lips soft and creating a light shine. However, the soft, brittle lipstick and poor color retention for colored lip balms are the remaining disadvantages of this lipstick line.

Wind Lipstick

This is a very special lipstick because the color on the lipstick and the color on the lips are not the same. Lipstick is a type of lipstick that changes color based on body temperature when applied to the lips. The ingredients in lipstick are dyes that react with pH and temperature.

In terms of advantages, this lipstick line can vary from person to person, this is the interesting and outstanding point of this lipstick line compared to other lipsticks. Besides, this is a lipstick that has good color adhesion, is long-lasting, and creates a smooth feeling on the lips. The downside of this lipstick line is that the color may not be as expected by the user, and with good color adhesion, the lipstick is difficult to remove for the user.

2.4. Vietnamese Gen Z and Consumer Habits

Generation Z

Gen Z is the group of people that follows on from previous generations such as Generation X and Y. According to researchers and media, Generation Z is young people born between 1995 and 2012. They are the first to have access to technology from a very young age and have a mindset about money, economics, technology and are quick to adapt to the times and can change the world in the future. (Bui Tuan An, n.d)

Consumption Habits of Vietnamese Gen Z Generation

Gen Z is a generation of smart consumers because thanks to their proficiency in information technology, Gen Z has the ability and ability to easily research and evaluate products. They often see more realistic reviews from influential people on social networks such as KOLs, Influencers...

When shopping online, they can go through websites, e-commerce platforms, mobile apps... to carefully consider their needs and whether the product is suitable for them or not, and also carefully consider the reviews of each person who has used the product.

In addition, Gen Z is a generation that tends to prioritize consuming environmentally friendly products. At the same time, Generation Z's shopping behavior is more about trends than buying for essential needs or products necessary for life.

Therefore, research on current consumer trends, along with the intentions and consumer behavior of young people, plays an important role for businesses. (Trang Vu, n.d)

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

To study "*Lipstick usage trends of Vietnamese Gen Z youth*", the research team used two research methods: desk research (reviewing published documents in the media) and sociological survey (collecting response forms from target subjects).

The data will be compiled and analyzed using Excel software. Using desk research methods, the research team reviewed documents on cosmetics, lipsticks, articles related to the trend of using cosmetics in general and lipsticks in particular among Vietnamese youth published in the media, and examined the characteristics of Vietnamese Gen Z youth.

From there, the research team proceeded to build a survey form to conduct a sociological investigation on lipstick usage trends among Vietnamese youth. Regarding the sociological investigation method, the research team conducted a preliminary survey and discussed with interested people who have used and are using lipstick. Discussion participants are free to express their opinions on aspects related to lipstick. The preliminary research sample size was 10 people.

The preliminary research results were used to complete the research questionnaire. After having a complete survey, the research team sent and collected the survey via the link on Google Form (<https://forms.gle/Xf4dqMHZH1V8h4Fr7>) combined with direct survey with young Vietnamese Gen Z people.

The data collection method was conducted by the research team based on the convenience sampling method and the "snowball" method (a method of finding the next subject based on the suggestion or introduction of the subject just interviewed) to ensure sufficient sample size as required. The number of survey ballots collected was 276, with 255 people using lipstick, the remaining 21 people have never or do not use lipstick.

4. RESEARCH RESULTS

4.1. General Information about Survey Participants

Figure 1: Age of Survey Subjects

Source: Survey results

Of the total 276 survey participants (research group focused on Vietnamese youth), ***The age group with the highest proportion is from 18 to under 22 years old with 111 people (40%),*** Next is from 22 to under 25 years old (22%), the number of young people under 16 years old and from 18 to under 22 years old account for an equal proportion (15-16%). The group ***over 25 years old has the lowest percentage with 18 people (7%).***

Figure 2: The reality of lipstick use

Source: Survey Results

Regarding the status of lipstick use, out of a total of 276 young people participating in the survey, there are **255 people (92%) are using lipstick**, The remaining 21 people (8%) said they do not use lipstick (Figure 2). And when asked about the reason for not using lipstick, the majority of opinions said that **Lipstick containing lead causes dry, dark lips** (21 people); 18 comments said that due to **school regulations, lipstick should not be used**. 15 reasons why you don't wear lipstick **do not have enough financial resources to use and 3 friends think that they simply don't like using lipstick** (Figure 3). It can be seen that, considering the regulations of the School and family, people under 16 years old and from 16 to under 18 years old will not use lipstick.

Figure 3: Reasons not to use lipstick

Source: Survey Results

However, among the 21 people who do not use lipstick, when asked if they will use lipstick in the future, the answer is **100% yes**, shows the growing popularity of lipstick and its influence on consumers, especially young people. It can be seen that lipstick is an important item for women and girls when going out.

4.2. Lipstick Usage Trends of Young People

Figure 4: Number of lipsticks owned by young people

Source: Survey Results

Of the 255 people who are using lipstick, most of them own from *1 – 3 lipstick in the makeup cabinet (66%)*; 78 people own 4-6 lipsticks in their makeup cabinet (31%) and 9 people own more than 6 lipsticks (3%). That shows that on average they all own *at least 1-3 lipsticks* in their makeup cabinet with a variety of colors and types.

Figure 5: Type of lipstick owned by survey respondents

Source: Survey Results

Regarding lipstick, most of them own and use *lip balm* (177 people) – *the highest percentage*. Next is *lip gloss* (with 150 people choosing); Cream lipstick and matte lipstick have the same popularity (111 people choose this lipstick line). The less known lipstick lines compared to the other lipstick lines are tint lipstick (27 people chose), *satin lipstick (21 people chose) and wind lipstick (3 people chose)*. It can be seen that young people use and own a variety of lipstick lines, the most prominent are popular lipstick lines such as lip balm, cream lipstick and matte lipstick.

Figure 6: Occasions of lipstick use by survey participants

Source: Survey Results

When asked about the occasions when young people use lipstick, the research team found that young people mainly use lipstick every day when going to school or work (213 opinions) and **147 people choose to use lipstick on formal occasions** such as birthdays, parties, going out... It can be seen that for the most part, lipstick plays an important role for young people as a daily makeup item, from normal occasions to special occasions such as parties or going out...

Figure 7: Origin of Lipstick Products that Survey Subjects are using

Source: Survey results

Of the 255 people who are using lipstick, when asked about the origin of the lipsticks they own, the majority of them are using lipsticks that are partly natural (**accounting for 49% of the total number of survey participants**); 81 people use conventional lipsticks (derived from chemicals) and the number of young people who own and use **lipsticks of completely natural origin accounts for the smallest** percentage (19%). That shows that young people are aware of the importance of lipsticks with natural, benign ingredients, but in general, with the products sold on the market today and with financial potential, most of them still use conventional lipstick products containing chemicals or lipsticks that are partly derived from nature but the chemical content still accounts for the majority of lipstick products.

Figure 8: Lipstick Selection Trends According to Body Characteristics of Survey Participants

Source: Survey Results

Regarding the lipstick selection trends of young people, **204 people choose lipstick according to age**. In actual observation, younger people tend to choose bright lipstick colors. Besides, **165 of you choose lipstick according to your skin color**, your skin color will determine the lipstick color you choose to use. In addition, **141 of you choose lipstick according to the occasion of use**. Maybe every day, you use a different type of lipstick, and on special occasions, you use a different type of lipstick... Young people’s lipstick selection trends also follow other trends such as choosing lipstick based on **hair color (66 people)**, choosing lipstick based on **lip shape and size (39 people)**, choosing lipstick based on **skin tone (15 people)**.

Figure 9: Lipstick Selection Criteria of Survey Participants

Source: Survey results

Regarding the lipstick selection criteria of the survey participants, most of you choose lipstick with a **color that suits your preferences and characteristics (204 people)**; next is **the benign and safe criteria** for the lips and health (with 174 people choosing). 78 people choose lipstick according to **trends**. The reason is that today’s young generation tends to consume products influenced by celebrities and those around them, often pushing a phenomenon into a trend or fad. Besides, some other criteria to consider when choosing lipstick are long lasting color, long lasting color, choosing lipstick with reasonable price.

Box 1. Lipstick colors leading the trend

Lipstick is a woman’s “weapon”. Representing beauty, charm and pride are what lipstick attracts others. Applying a lipstick color that suits you will make you conquer all eyes.

Women often choose their favorite lipstick color to express their own style, mood and personality, so it is not an exaggeration to say that lipstick is a beauty statement for women. Beautiful lipstick trends make many girls attracted by their attractiveness and irresistible charm.

Every girl is “knocked out” by the charming, passionate wine lipstick color. This delicate lipstick color will give her lips a classic, noble look. Besides, this is the perfect lipstick color

for parties or when attending events.

Fashion and beauty are tending to return to old values. So dark lipstick is extremely loved by the followers. With lip liner, brown lipstick and a coat of gloss you have completed the 90s look.

One way to freshen up your look is to use red lipstick and glitter effects. Red has the ability to lift skin tone wonderfully and the glitter particles coated on the lips will have the effect of catching light and highlighting the appearance. Although not widely popular, black lipstick is indispensable for Gothic, rock-chic or rebellious ladies. This is a color that brings mysterious, magical beauty and captivating appeal. Nude lipstick is increasingly popular with followers thanks to the “makeup no makeup” trend that is popular. The fact that it suits all skin tones and brings a gentle, clear look is what makes nude lipstick a must-have item in your cosmetic bag. Purple red lipstick makes women look extremely powerful and full of charisma. Designed specifically for women over 30 who want to add a more “salty” impression to their appearance. Classic red lipstick is always an indispensable color and is at the top of the beauty trends of girls. Red lipstick symbolizes the beauty, boldness and pride of women. In particular, this lipstick color also whitens the skin and teeth, so it is very “worshiped”. It is not very practical and is usually only used at performance events such as catwalks, festivals, etc. Metallic lipstick is suitable for girls who are playful, unconventional and are true fashionistas. For ladies who love pure baby beauty, peach pink is the most suitable choice. You can apply an additional layer of lip gloss on the outside to create a dreamy, “cool” beauty for your appearance.

Source: Bach Nhat (2023)

Figure 10: Concerns about lipstick use among young people

Source: Survey results

One of the biggest concerns when using lipstick among young people is that regular lipstick can affect the lips and health because lipstick products **contain lead and some other chemicals in the cosmetics industry (with 240 choices)**. Nowadays, many products, goods in general and lipstick in particular are sold on the market, so the next concern is that the **origin of lipstick**

products is unclear and difficult to verify the quality and origin (207 people). In addition, some other concerns are the difficulty in choosing the right lipstick color or that safe, high-quality lipsticks are often expensive...

Figure 11: Want to use lipsticks that are completely natural in the future

Source: Survey results

Nowadays, with the rise of the trend of protecting the environment and using products that are completely natural, benign and not tested on animals, when asked about their intention to use lipstick products like the above but with more expensive prices or not, 99% of you agree to use *lipstick lines with natural origins even though the prices are more expensive*. That shows that today's youth value environmentally friendly and health-safe products more than the price of the product itself.

5. DISCUSSION

The lipstick market in particular and cosmetics in general in Vietnam are increasingly vibrant and highly competitive. To promote the development of the lipstick market, based on customer factors through the research, young people are the main and potential customers for the lipstick market in Vietnam, grasping the lipstick selection trends of young Vietnamese people, the research team offers some solutions to promote the development of the lipstick market in Vietnam as follows:

First, need to focus on promoting development and improving product quality. Looking at the actual trend, it can be seen that young people are increasingly interested in lipstick lines that are natural, safe and benign. Using ingredients extracted from plants is not only good for health but also creates a unique lipstick product compared to other common lipsticks. In addition, lipstick lines need to increase color durability, moisturizing ability and lip protection. And to do this, manufacturers need to apply new technologies to production to create smart, convenient products such as temperature-changing lipstick, colored lip balm, etc.

Second, through the survey, the research team found that young people's choice of lipstick color is also very diverse and depends on many factors. Therefore, lipstick brands do not just stop at basic colors, but need to constantly create new, unique tones that are suitable for fashion trends and personality, meeting many consumer conditions. Manufacturers can pay attention to some lipstick trends in the market today such as: colored lip balm by combining lip balm and colored lipstick, meeting the needs of beauty and lip care; Long-lasting matte lipsticks are suitable for busy people who do not have much time to reapply lipstick; organic lipsticks are extracted from natural ingredients, suitable for sensitive skin; custom lipsticks allow customers to choose their own colors and ingredients.

Third, the use of lipstick and the selection of lipstick characteristics also depend on KOLs and KOCs because the characteristics of Vietnamese youth are consumers who are influenced by influential people and easily become trendsetters. Therefore, brands need to take advantage of the power of social networking platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, Tiktok to reach young customers by creating creative marketing campaigns, using influencers to create a ripple effect. At the same time, it is necessary to promote the organization of activities, product launch events, beauty workshops, and direct product experiences to create a strong impression on customers. Brands can refer to some branding methods for lipstick products such as creating stories close to life so that customers can relate and stick with the brand. In addition, build a community of loyal users through social media groups, offline events, customer appreciation programs; cooperate with other brands to create unique products and reach new customers.

Fourth, brands need to step up updating the latest beauty trends and youth trends in the market to be able to distribute lipstick lines that suit the times. Besides, it is necessary to set prices suitable for product quality and affordability of young people, creating lipstick lines corresponding to market segments. On the other hand, environmental issues and animal testing need to be taken into consideration in order to produce lipstick products that meet the criteria set by today's youth. In addition to safe, environmentally friendly lipstick products, brands can also use packaging or production processes that are green, safe, and environmentally friendly, and do not test on animals.

Fifth, regarding the distribution of lipstick products to Gen Z youth in particular and consumers in general, brands need to integrate online and offline sales channels to create diverse shopping experiences for customers. In particular, Vietnamese Gen Z youth are customers who have access to modern scientific and technological achievements and social networks, so online shopping is considered a habit for this generation. In addition, brands can organize pop-up stores in busy locations such as shopping malls and densely populated urban areas to increase interaction with customers in general and Vietnamese Gen Z youth in particular.

6. CONCLUSION

The study points out the main trends in the selection and use of lipstick lines by Vietnamese Gen Z youth. Through the survey results, the research team found that the trend of using lipstick among young people is increasingly diverse in terms of design, quality, lipstick color and especially the trend of using environmentally friendly lipstick lines, with benign ingredients

and safe for health. The study shows which criteria Gen Z youth tend to choose lipstick based on, choose lipstick color according to body characteristics, choose lipstick according to usage occasions... and also explores the concerns of young people when using common lipstick products today. Thereby, the article has proposed a number of exchanges and discussions to promote and develop the lipstick market based on surveys, needs and desires of young people, helping manufacturers and distributors of lipstick products to be able to meet the lipstick lines that are suitable to the trends and requirements of Gen Z youth in particular and consumers in general.

References

- 1) Bach Nhat (2023). *Lipstick colors that are leading the trend*. <https://thanhvien.vn/thoi-trang-tre/nhung-mau-son-moi-dang-dan-dau-xu-huong-185230320213834328.htm>
- 2) Bio Cosmetics (n.d). *What is lipstick? Things you need to know about lipstick*. <https://biocosmetics.vn/giai-phap/son-moi-la-gi-nhung-kien-thuc-ve-son-can-biet.html>
- 3) Bui Tuan An (2023). *What is Gen Z? What is Generation Z? What is special about Generation Z?*. <https://luatminhkhue.vn/gen-z-la-gi.aspx>
- 4) Danh Nguyen Tran (2022). *Research on the popularity of cosmetics and its future in Vietnam market*. Quality - Access to Success, 2022, Vol 23, Issue 186, p19. <https://biocosmetics.vn/giai-phap/son-moi-la-gi-nhung-kien-thuc-ve-son-can-biet.html>
- 5) Elly (2022). *5 lipstick trends for young people in 2022*. <https://elly.vn/5-xu-huong-son-moi-cua-gioi-tre-2022/?srsltid=AfmBOorkyDi14Ehx5QhuJ-Za-3bngjCQndiMy1WjcXbMfIZ0wouB8e-6>
- 6) M.O.I Cosmetics (2023). *Tips on lipsticks that are popular with young people*. https://moicosmetics.vn/blogs/bi-quyet-khoe-dep/son-moi-duoc-gioi-tre-ua-chuong?srsltid=AfmBOop_mWA1D8FmfFGLX3sXO6Zq5arS5XS9a2wphoH3bzWNIKSWU7jr
- 7) M.O.I Cosmetics (n.d). *What is lipstick? Do you know how to distinguish different types of lipstick?* https://moicosmetics.vn/blogs/xu-huong-trang-diem/cac-loai-son-moi?srsltid=AfmBOooZnO0oV9x8NNAod6tJ15jgbb-2RbREMidVyTVSWLw1EcL_EyO
- 8) Madeleine Ogilvie and Pauline Kristensen-Bach (2001). *Why women wear lipstick: preliminary findings*. https://www.researchgate.net/profile/M-Ogilvie/publication/49282703_Why_women_wear_lipstick_preliminary_findings/links/55430a490cf24107d3948d9e/Why-women-wear-lipstick-preliminary-findings.pdf
- 9) Pía López-Jornet, Fabio Camacho-Alonso, Ana Rodríguez-Espin (2010). *Study of lip hydration with application of photoprotective lipstick: Influence of skin phototype, size of lips, age, sex and smoking habits*. Med Oral Patol Oral Cir Bucal. 2010 May 1;15 (3):e445-50.
- 10) Tran Thi Huong (2016). *The project of Facebook marketing campaign for Rohto Vietnam (Miracle Apo Lipstick)*. <http://digilib.k.utb.cz/handle/10563/40562>
- 11) Trang Vu (n.d). *Understanding the shopping habits of Gen Z customers – the main customers in the near future*. <https://subiz.com.vn/blog/thoi-quen-mua-sam-cua-gen-z.html>
- 12) Vinmec (n.d). *Ingredients of lipstick*. <https://www.vinmec.com/vie/bai-viet/cac-thanh-phan-cua-son-moi-vi>
- 13) VKI (n.d). *Overview of the cosmetics market in Vietnam*. <https://vki.vn/tong-quan-thi-truong-my-pham-tai-viet-nam/>